

Conductometric Titration of Barium with Potassium Tellurite

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Conductometric titration of barium with potassium tellurite in presence of an overall concentration of 40-50% ethanol has been described. Direct as well as reverse titrations are shown to be possible over a wide range of barium concentrations and the effect of varying ethanol concentrations is reported. Conductometric study lends support to the 1:1 molar ratio of Ba and Te.

Lenher and Wolensky¹ prepared and studied the properties of tellurites of K, Na, Ag, Ba, Mg, Cd, Ni, Co, Mn, Pb, and NH_4^+ . They prepared the normal and ditellurites of sodium and potassium by heating TeO_2 with calculated quantities of Na_2CO_3 and K_2CO_3 and their tetratellurites by the decomposition of ditellurites with water; the tellurites of other metals were prepared by precipitation from solutions of their salts with sodium tellurite. Barium tellurite was obtained as a white precipitate.

The present communication reports the results of conductometric titrations of barium with potassium tellurite under varied experimental conditions in some detail.

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium tellurite solution was obtained by dissolving the B.D.H. reagent grade sample in conductivity water and the tellurium content determined by the usual gravimetric procedure². The strength of barium chloride solution, prepared by dissolving 'AnalaR' sample, was 0.0859*M*.

Wissenschaftliche Technische Werkstätten (WTW) conductivity meter type LBR/B, a 220 volt, A.C. line operated, direct reading electronic instrument with a magic eye as the zero indicator was used for conductance measurements. The readings were recorded in mhos at 50 cycles. The conductometric titration cell WTW type LTI, having platinised platinum electrodes and a 2 ml microburette, was connected to the terminal "cell" on the meter. The main switch was turned "on" and the selector switch to mhos for recording the conductance directly. The instrument was set for zero loss angle and highest sensitivity.

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 718.

2. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green & Co. Inc., New York, 2nd ed., 1953, p. 310.

The range switch was moved to the expected range and the pointer knob rotated till the magic eye showed the maximum shadow angle. The scale value was now read and multiplied by the factor indicated on the range selector switch to find the conductance directly.

Direct Conductometric Titration

A known volume of barium chloride solution containing overall concentration of 40-50% ethanol was taken in the conductivity titration cell placed on a magnetic stirrer and the initial conductance of the solution noted. Potassium tellurite solution was added from a microburette in small amounts to barium chloride solution, the mixture stirred well, and the precipitate allowed to settle for a definite interval of time before recording the conductance reading. The temperature was maintained at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$ by circulating water from a constant temperature water bath in the jacket provided in the cell for the purpose. Volume correction³ was applied before plotting these observed values of conductance against the volume of the titrant. The results are plotted in Figs. 1 and 2 (curves I-IX).

FIG. 1

Reverse Conductometric Titration

In the titration of potassium tellurite against barium chloride solution, a known volume of potassium tellurite solution containing ethanol was taken in the conductivity cell and barium chloride solution added from the microburette. The rest of the procedure was the same as for the direct titration. Fig. 3 (curves I-III) shows the results of reverse titration.

Effect of Variation of Ethanol Concentration.—During the course of investigation the addition of ethanol was found essential for successful titration. The effect of variation of ethanol concentration on the conductometric titration of barium as tellurite was therefore studied. These results (Fig. 4, curves a-f) show that the break in the curve is sharper and consequently the end point is well defined in the presence of 40-50% overall concentration of ethanol. The results obtained are embodied in Table I.

TABLE I

Expt. No.	Vol. of BaCl ₂ solution.	Molarity of BaCl ₂ solution.	Vol. of K ₂ TeO ₃ solution.	Molarity of K ₂ TeO ₃ solution.	Molar ratio. Ba: Te.
Direct conductometric titration.					
1	25.00 ml	0.003430 M	0.975 ml	0.0895 M	1 : 1.0018
2	25.00	0.005154	1.450	0.08950	1 : 0.9933
3	25.00	0.001718	0.487	0.08950	1 : 1.0008
4	25.00	0.002577	0.735	0.08950	1 : 1.0088
5	20.00	0.004295	0.965	0.08950	1 : 0.9915
6	30.00	0.004253	1.465	0.08950	1 : 1.0036
7	25.00	0.001718	0.975	0.04475	1 : 1.0018
8	25.00	0.002148	1.220	0.04475	1 : 1.0028
9	25.00	0.002577	1.450	0.04475	1 : 0.9933
Reverse conductometric titration.					
10	0.515	0.0859	25.00	0.001790	1 : 1.0023
11	1.030	0.0859	25.00	0.003580	1 : 1.0024
12	1.550	0.0859	25.00	0.005970	1 : 1.0065
Effect of ethanol concentration.					
13 (aq.)	25.00	0.003436	0.695	0.0895	1 : 0.7141
14 (20% EtOH)	25.00	0.003436	0.960	0.0895	1 : 0.9864
15 (10% ")	25.00	0.003436	0.970	0.0895	1 : 0.9967
16 (80% ")	25.00	0.003436	0.975	0.0895	1 : 1.0018
17 (70% ")	25.00	0.003436	0.980	0.0895	1 : 1.0069
18 (80% ")	25.00	0.003436	0.985	0.0895	1 : 1.0121

DISCUSSION

The reaction involved in the direct conductometric titration of barium with potassium tellurite may be represented as:

The precipitation of barium tellurite in aqueous solution was not quantitative, presumably because of partial dissolution or hydrolysis of barium tellurite. Addition of ethanol improved the results markedly, due perhaps to the reduced solubility of the precipitate.

FIG. 4.

In both direct and reverse titrations, the break in conductance corresponds to the molar ratio 1:1 for Ba and Te. Under the conditions described, only normal barium tellurite is formed. The procedure affords a convenient means of titrimetric determination of barium.

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